

AIR FORCE LOGISTICS COMMAND'S VERY HIGH SPEED INTEGRATED CIRCUITS (VHSIC)
INSERTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

As Very High Speed Integrated Circuits (VHSIC) technology becomes popular in Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC), interest is flourishing to identify ground and airborne electronic systems already fielded which could benefit by VHSIC insertion. A background of the AFLC VHSIC program will be described from its conception in the Department of Defense to its present day status. Current AFLC programs will be discussed as they relate to the VHSIC program. Additionally, several candidate systems, which have been identified with the potential for VHSIC insertion, will be briefly highlighted. The paper will also address the impediments AFLC faces in inserting VHSIC technology quickly and effectively in fielded weapon systems. Supportability issues such as repair, testing, and procurement will be identified as they pose serious challenges for AFLC.

BACKGROUND

In March 1980, the Department of Defense began the VHSIC program for developing advanced silicon integrated circuits.(3) Before that time, DoD spent several years carefully assessing its needs and deficiencies in this area of technology. To accomplish the goals of the VHSIC program, three phases were proposed. Phase 1 effort concentrated on developing a microelectronic chip technology characterized by feature sizes as small as 1.25 microns and minimum operating frequency of 25 MHz. After the successful development of the 1.25 micron technology and its transition into products accomplished, the VHSIC program proposed the Phase 2 submicron program aimed at developing a second generation of silicon chips that are characterized by .5 micron feature sizes and a clock frequency of 100 MHz. Finally, Phase 3 efforts would develop supporting technologies. These would include advanced high resolution lithography, automated design aids, improved materials, self testing and fault tolerant design, packaging, and testing. On 7 November 1983, HQ AFLC/CC directed AFLC program management responsibilities for VHSIC to the Sacramento Air Logistics Center (SM-ALC). The were tasked to maintain a VHSIC engineering capability, to propose and develop language standards, design, and repair techniques, software standards, testing concepts, and computer aided design criteria. All these efforts are aimed at accelerating the infusion of VHSIC into AFLC managed weapon systems. To further accelerate the transition of VHSIC technology to operational systems and enhance supportability, the Technology Application Program Management (TAPM) program was

started in 1985. The VHSIC TAPM is just one of 17 TAPMs responsible for transitioning mature laboratory technologies to AFLC. Sacramento Air Logistics Center, located at McClellan Air Force Base, California, has been assigned the VHSIC TAPM, and their objective is to facilitate the transition of new technology into operational AFLC fielded weapon systems. An additional objective is to influence the development of the technology with emphasis on long term supportability.

AFLC VHSIC INSERTION PROJECTS

Presently, there are several VHSIC insertion projects in AFLC. The Digital Signal Transfer Unit (DSTU) on the F-111 is an AFLC VHSIC insertion success story. To accomplish the objective of the VHSIC project, a 1970's technology circuit card was replaced with a VHSIC chip and several other components. The VHSIC card reduces the parts count from 224 to 66, with an improvement in the reliability from 40 hours MTBF to a projected 5000 hours. Built-In-Test (BIT) is designed into the circuit card with 98 per cent fault isolation. The DSTU is being tested at Cannon Air Force Base, New Mexico.

The VHSIC Transistor Transistor Logic (TTL) Gate Array program is addressing integrated circuit (IC) technology obsolescence. Because the entire 54XX series of integrated circuits is becoming increasingly obsolete, the VHSIC TTL Gate Array is designed to replace 99 per cent of this series. This is accomplished through personalization of a silicon wafer to represent the desired 54XX chip. The wafer is overlaid with a metallic mask that allows the silicon wafer to emulate the desired 54XX chip.

The ALQ-131 VHSIC Transmit Control Assembly (VTCA) has gone through design and test and is awaiting infusion into blocks I and II. Implementation is planned for Aug 1988 and reliability on this system is expected to improve 25 percent. The Air Force initiated the program to insert VHSIC technology, from the DoD Phase I VHSIC program, into the ALQ-131 Electronics Counter Measures (ECM) pod. A single prototype VHSIC Transmit Control Assembly (VTCA) common to all three bands has been developed and integrated with the ALQ-131 Block I ECM pod. The current VTCA is a functional replacement for the Block I TCA, yet it provides growth space and power for additional functions. Figure 1 provides a comparison between today's TCAs and tomorrow's VTCA's. The ALQ-131 Block II ECM pod incorporates additional capabilities that require added transmit control functions and currently has a unique, fully populated TCA configuration for each ECM pod band. The VTCA design allows the addition of Block II TCA functions to the current Block I VTCA through insertion of a additional VHSIC-

based printed circuit card, while retaining additional growth space.

ALQ-131 POD

<u>TODAY'S TCAS</u>	<u>TOMORROW'S VTCAS</u>
FOUR DISSIMILAR ASSEMBLIES	SIX IDENTICAL ASSEMBLIES
54 TYPES OF CARDS/ 4 CHASSIS	9 TYPES OF CARDS/ 1 CHASSIS
44 CARDS PER BLOCK I POD	24 CARDS PER BLOCK I POD
47 CARDS PER BLOCK II POD	27 CARDS PER BLOCK II POD
NO ROOM FOR GROWTH	ROOM FOR ADDITIONAL GROWTH

Figure 1. Comparison of TCAs (Ref. 2)

A VHSIC insertion for the B-52 Stability Augmentation System (SAS) is presently ongoing. The objective of the program is to develop form-fit-function digital equivalents for the B-52 SAS Yaw and Pitch Electronic Control Units. A PACE MIL-STD-1750 CPU, which is a VHSIC device, will be incorporated into the design. Benefits of the program include higher reliability due to lower power consumption and increased performance due to higher computation rates. Delivery of the system is anticipated for Oct 88.

Within Cheyenne Mountain, the 1960's designed communications multiplexer is very unreliable and is becoming unsupportable due to parts obsolescence. The objective of this project is to replace the switching interface assembly in the General Data Nova 2 mini-computer with a modular, fault tolerant system using VHSIC. Additionally, this project will demonstrate the feasibility of using common modules between different ground based systems. Implementation of the new switching interface assembly is scheduled for March 1990. Reliability is predicted to increase from 200 hours to 2000-5000 hours. The line replaceable modules within this project are to be interchangeable with another project which is called SEEK IGL00, or FPS-117 Minimally Attended Radar.

Supportability of the FPS-117 Signal Processing Unit is a problem because of its remote location. VHSIC is being inserted into the FPS-117 to improve reliability and maintainability. The project provides for the form, fit, and function replacement of the signal processing unit within the FPS-117 radar at each remote radar site location. The first phase will accomplish baseline system design for data and signal processing and includes software development. The second phase involves integration, system verification, and final acceptance testing. Lastly, the third phase addresses production and development of system modification kits.

AFLC PROPOSED PROJECTS

In addition to the current AFLC projects, the five Air Logistics Centers (ALCs) have identified

eleven potential VHSIC candidates which are presently under evaluation at SM-ALC. These can be seen in Figure 2.

<u>SYSTEM NAME</u>	
1	F-15 AND F-16 CNI REPLACEMENT
2	CHEYENNE MOUNTAIN ELECTRONIC CARD
3	B-1B TERRAIN FOLLOWING RADAR ADAPTER
4	B-1B RADAR SIGNAL PROCESSOR
5	F-15 AND F-16 RING LASER GYRO
<u>SYSTEM NAME</u>	
6	F-15 ALR 56C RWR PROCESSOR
7	F-15 APG-63 RADAR SIGNAL PROCESSOR
8	F-111 STORES MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
9	KC-135 FUEL SAVINGS ADVISORY SYSTEM
10	A-7 DIGITAL FLIGHT CONTROL SYSTEM
11	F-15 IFF/UHF/VHF REPLACEMENT

Figure 2. Proposed VHSIC Projects

This office has proposed a modular electronic infusion on at least two different aircraft types, preferably the F-15 and F-16, to baseline the AFLC infrastructure for modular electronics subsystems, ground support, and test equipment. Another candidate is a terminal and electronic card in the Cheyenne Mountain Complex. The user, who is Space Command, has asked for this to be replaced or upgraded and SM-ALC has recommended a VHSIC replacement. Current reliability on the B-1B Terrain Following Adapter, which feeds data to the flight control system is extremely poor. VHSIC insertion would increase reliability, lower power requirements, and provide room for additional growth in the system. The B-1B Radar Signal Processor project would prototype VHSIC technology to enhance the AN/APQ-164, part of the B-1B Offensive Radar System. The current system is experiencing low reliability. VHSIC insertion on the F-16 and F-15 Ring Laser Gyro Navigation Systems relative to signal processing has been suggested and would increase sampling rate and improve navigation calculations. Reliability would also be improved. Two additional VHSIC candidates on the F-15 are the ALR-56 Radar Warning Receiver Processor and the APG-63 Radar Programmable Signal Processor. No other information is available on these two projects. A proposal to insert VHSIC into the F-111 Stores Management System (SMS) was recommended by a General Dynamics study. Conclusions from the study determined that the SMS would benefit in

reliability and maintainability from a VHSIC insertion. Modernization of the KC-135 Fuel Savings Advisory System with VHSIC will increase reliability and provide better supportability and maintainability. Another proposed candidate is the A-7 Digital Flight Control System. A VHSIC insertion would replace the current analog flight control system with a digital system. Finally, AFLC has a plan to design and develop a replacement for the IFF/UHF/VHF portion of the F-15 avionics suite using integrated modular electronics. However beneficial it is to pursue these proposed projects, it is important to be aware of the impediments which slow VHSIC insertion.

IMPEDIMENTS

Not understanding a technology's capabilities has often been a cause in the past for program managers in AFLC not to use new technology. The same goes for VHSIC. A lack of information on VHSIC and circulation of incorrect information has contributed to this misunderstanding. There is also a lack of confidence in a new technology without a long track record of performance, and many program and item managers consider VHSIC to be still in transition from research and development to marketing a finished product. It is through the infusion of VHSIC and education of our middle management engineers and non-technical personnel that this problem is solved.

Funding for developmental efforts using VHSIC devices is not readily available for VHSIC insertions in AFLC. Identifying and removing impediments are important to the AFLC VHSIC program, however several challenges exist in the area of support.

SUPPORTABILITY

AFLC is primarily concerned with supportability in the areas of testability, repair, and reprourement.(1) Testability may be resident in three layers of the VHSIC weapon system. The first level is Built-In-Test (BIT) on the chip. The BIT on the chip is useless without the on board maintenance node or system level maintenance monitor with the necessary software to exercise the test. A great deal of software must be developed that provides the protocols for exercising the BIT during off peak periods, and for maintaining the fault data for later repair information as well as providing the data for identifying and isolating the faults when they occur. The second level is resident at the board/module. This is where the bulk of the fault isolation will occur, as well as local area maintenance monitoring. These monitors watch the operation of the modules and let the maintenance controller know when to download test software to exercise the chips or boards. A maintenance module will also provide overall management of all fault data, test software, and test timing. This is equivalent to low level, functional testing. The third level of test is within the subsystem itself. Integration with the system operationai

software will be extremely important for the test while the system is operational. In addition, system integration certification must be conducted, where modules and systems run real code in a real time environment.

Repair techniques are going to change with VHSIC technology. Two level, and even one level maintenance has been proposed for future weapon systems. The critical element is the on-chip test that will be available for system designers to use for board and system level test and maintenance functions. Surface mount technology has also changed rapidly in recent years. Wire wrap and printed wiring boards were common 10 years ago. Now we see multi-layer ceramic and multi-layer printed circuit boards. The physics associated with heat transfer, and the removal and replacement of the chips has changed due to these new techniques. Therefore, AFLC must plan to support these changes also. A major issue with one level maintenance is the "throwaway item". With one level maintenance, the Line Replaceable Module (LRM) becomes throwaway, removing the need for many depot level functions. The testability of the chips and systems, and the redundancy and reconfigurability will all influence the total life cycle cost. If there is viable BIT on the chip, then the LRM repair becomes an issue. There is also research being conducted at the University of Oregon to develop repair capability, raising still another repair and maintenance issue. If repair is conducted at the chip, module, or system level, then repair verification procedures must be implemented. Verification will consist of two levels. The first level is a "low level" test to validate "go" or "no go" of the chip or board. This test will be implemented after repair to verify that the item will function as required. The second level involves the weapon system verification. The test will actually load the system software onto a board for functional verification. For example, the system would now be tested as a radar signal processor. Additionally, advanced Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) will be needed to test VHSIC systems at the depot level. System hardware must have greater speed than VHSIC to ensure adequate testing at all levels. Software is another issue. Software will have to be written for both the test program sets, which interface between the test equipment and Unit Under Test (UUT), and the ATE itself.

Reprourement data must be accurate and complete. Chip level data must be obtained and used to verify the chips as they come from procurement activities. Complete, accurate chip data will assure the availability of replacement components for boards and systems even after they become obsolete. Necessary chip data includes netlists, test vector sets, test programs, functional specifications, timing and speed, input/output characteristics, and the VHSIC Hardware Description Language (VHDL). For system level, accurate Technical Orders (TOs) for hardware specifications must be provided. However, just as important, is the specification of the operational and test software. Test vector sets and test programs must be provided to verify

that the hardware performs as specified.

In conclusion, AFLC System Program Managers (SPMs) and Item Managers (IMs) must be made aware that Phase I VHSIC is ready for infusion into their weapon systems. This is already being reflected to some extent by the numerous ongoing VHSIC insertion programs. AFLC is also teaming with industry to facilitate the application of VHSIC into AFLC managed systems. We are working with TRW, Honeywell, IBM, Singer, and Texas Instruments to identify and propose VHSIC insertion candidates to this command. We are taking a proactive approach to further identify VHSIC insertion candidates through AFLC SPMs and IMs and this is reflected in the candidates already identified.

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